

Comprehensive Evaluation of the Solar-Powered Street Lighting System Along the Sibulan–Dumaguete Diversion Road in Negros Oriental: Basis for System Enhancement

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Index Terms:

solar street lighting, illuminance level, lighting uniformity, pole alignment, road safety

Abstract. This study evaluated the performance and reliability of the solar-powered street lighting system along the Bajumpandan segment of the Sibulan–Dumaguete Diversion Road to establish a basis for system enhancement. Utilizing a descriptive-correlational research design, field measurements were conducted across a 300-meter road segment using calibrated digital lux meters, supported by technical component inspections and an analysis of official accident records. The results revealed a critical lighting failure, with several measurement points recording zero to near-zero lux, indicating significant system underperformance and widespread darkness. Detailed component assessments further identified inefficiencies in solar charging, battery storage, and luminaire output as the primary drivers of unstable nighttime illumination. Statistical analysis using Spearman’s rho indicated a very weak positive relationship between illuminance levels and vehicle accident rates. Correlation analysis using Spearman’s rho yielded a p-value of 0.945; thus, the study failed to reject the null hypothesis, indicating no significant statistical relationship between illuminance levels and vehicle accidents within the Bajumpandan segment. However, the findings indicate that road safety is a multi-layered issue influenced by design quality, uniformity, and human factors. The study concludes that the existing infrastructure is technically inadequate and recommends a comprehensive upgrade to LED luminaires and improved photovoltaic systems, alongside optimized pole alignment and regular maintenance programs to ensure consistent roadway safety and operational reliability.

Introduction

Inadequate road lighting is a critical global infrastructure and energy challenge, affecting mobility, driver comfort, and the safe use of transport corridors, particularly at night (Ayaz et al., 2024). Across many countries, long stretches of highways, diversion roads, and rural routes remain poorly illuminated or completely unlit, forcing drivers to rely primarily on vehicle headlights (Chen et al., 2024). Limited visibility reduces the ability to detect roadway alignment, hazards, pedestrians, and other vehicles, contributing to higher rates of nighttime accidents (Sari & Yudhistira, 2021). These lighting deficiencies are often linked to rising electricity costs, limited government budgets, and the technical challenges of implementing reliable lighting systems in developing or peripheral areas, highlighting a persistent worldwide problem (Wicaksono et al., 2021).

To address this global challenge, many countries have adopted energy-efficient lighting technologies to improve nighttime visibility, enhance road safety, and reduce energy consumption (Ylinen et al., 2011). Solar-powered and LED-based street lighting systems have emerged as practical alternatives to traditional grid-connected luminaires, offering dependable illumination even in areas with unstable or limited grid access while reducing energy costs (Asalar & Ujevverume, 2016). By harnessing locally available solar energy and storing it for nighttime use, these systems are particularly suitable for regions with high solar irradiance and constrained infrastructure budgets (Nixon et al., 2021). However, their effectiveness

depends on proper design, including pole spacing, mounting height, illuminance levels, battery capacity, and regular maintenance, as poorly designed or maintained systems may fail to provide sufficient lighting, increasing accident risks (Perdahci & Ozkan, 2019).

In the Philippine context, many national highways and diversion roads outside major urban centers continue to experience uneven or inadequate street lighting, reflecting similar financial and technical challenges observed globally (Gonocruz et al., 2023). While metropolitan areas have begun integrating modern and energy-efficient lighting (Antonio Jr. et al., 2024), provincial roads often rely on minimal solar-powered installations that do not provide consistent illumination (Maroma & Pangilinan, 2018). Rising electricity costs and budget limitations further constrain the expansion of conventional grid-based systems, emphasizing the need for well-planned solar-powered alternatives capable of independent operation (Roxas & Santiago, 2016). These local realities mirror the broader global challenge of providing reliable, sustainable, and energy-efficient roadway lighting, underscoring the importance of localized evaluations (Gulagi et al., 2021). The Sibulan-Dumaguete Diversion Road in Negros Oriental exemplifies a local case of this global issue. Serving as a strategic bypass for Dumaguete City and accommodating cargo trucks, public utility vehicles, private cars, and motorcycles, the corridor requires dependable nighttime illumination to enhance safety and reduce accidents (Bartolo et al., 2023). Inadequate illuminance from existing or underperforming solar-powered lighting contributes directly to higher nighttime accident rates along the route (Mejorada et al., 2023). By evaluating the system's performance, adequacy, and areas for improvement using locally gathered data, this study contributes to the United Nations Sustainable Development Goal 7 (Affordable and Clean Energy) by promoting renewable energy integration, reducing reliance on conventional electricity, and ensuring reliable, sustainable, and energy-efficient nighttime roadway illumination (Abdullah et al., 2024).

Statement of the Problem

This study aims to assess the lighting conditions and illuminance levels along the Bajumpandan segment Sibulan-Dumaguete Diversion Road to determine whether the existing street lighting complies with recommended standards for nighttime visibility and road safety, and to provide recommendations for improvement based on the findings.

Specifically, the study seeks to address the following concerns:

1. What are the current lighting conditions of the existing street lighting along the Bajumpandan area of Sibulan-Dumaguete Diversion Road.
2. What factors influence the functional illumination levels along the Bajumpandan Segment in the Sibulan-Dumaguete Diversion Road in term of:
 - 2.1 Environmental Factors
 - 2.2 Technical Factors
3. What is the vehicle accident rate in identified high-risk areas along the Bajumpandan segment of the Sibulan-Dumaguete Diversion Road?
4. Is there significant relationship between the vehicle accident rate and the current lighting conditions of the existing street lighting along the Bajumpandan segment Sibulan-Dumaguete Diversion Road?
5. Based on the findings of the study, what recommendations can be proposed to improve road lighting and nighttime visibility along the Bajumpandan segment Sibulan-Dumaguete Diversion Road?

Statement of Null Hypothesis

There is no significant relationship between the vehicle accident rate and the current lighting conditions and illuminance level of the existing street lighting along the Bajumpandan segment Sibulan-Dumaguete Diversion Road.

Methodology

This study was employing a quantitative research design to evaluate the existing lighting conditions along the Sibulan-Dumaguete Diversion Road. Data were collected through observations and measurements of technical factors such as illuminance, uniformity, pole spacing, and height, as well as environmental factors including tree shading, cloud cover, and other obstructions. This approach provides a detailed understanding of areas with inadequate or inconsistent lighting.

Research Environment

The study was conducted along the Sibulan-Dumaguete Diversion Road in Negros Oriental, specifically in Bajumpandan segment, which is a primary bypass route used by heavy cargo trucks and private vehicles to avoid Dumaguete City. The road passes through interior barangays such as Magatas and Boloc-Boloc, extending to Dumaguete. It features wide lanes, varying elevations, and several "black spots", or unlit areas identified as high-risk zones for nighttime accidents. The road

carries a mix of traffic, including multi-axle trucks, motorcycles, and private vehicles. Extensive segments lack centralized street lighting, creating hazardous nighttime conditions, especially between 6:00 PM and 5:00 AM, when driver perception-reaction time is severely compromised due to low visibility. Artificial grid lighting in certain areas (e.g., Bajumpandan) is managed independently by the barangay. These additional light sources could significantly impact the overall lighting measurements. Additional hazards include stray animals and unlit roadside obstacles. Sibulan- Dumaguete Diversion Road was selected due to its critical role in the provincial road network and the presence of unlit high-risk segments. Preliminary data from the PNP and BFP indicate that infrastructure deficiencies, primarily lack of street illumination, significantly contribute to nighttime accidents. Evaluating solar-powered street lighting along this corridor aims to improve visibility and overall road safety.

Scope

Location: Selected segments of the Sibulan–Dumaguete Diversion Road, specifically the Bajumpandan section toward Dumaguete City.

Data Sources: Traffic Accident Investigation Reports (TAIR) and emergency logs (PNP/BFP) from 2023–2025.

Technical Design: Standalone off-grid solar LED systems (7:00pm-4:00am operation) with 3.5-day autonomy based on NASA POWER irradiance data.

Assessment: Technical system sizing, empirical lux measurements (up to two decimal places), and general cost estimation.

Limitations

Geographic: Analysis excludes the entire length of the diversion road, focusing only on identified high-risk segments.

Behavioral/Mechanical: Excludes non-infrastructure accident factors such as driver intoxication, speeding, or vehicle mechanical failure.

System Type: Excludes grid-tied, hybrid solar-grid systems, or alternative renewables (wind/biomass).

Environmental/Social: Excludes battery disposal management, light pollution impacts on wildlife, and subjective data collection (surveys/questionnaires).

Spatial/Temporal: Excludes continuous 24-hour monitoring; measurements are limited to specific points and time intervals.

Research Instruments

The following instruments ensure accuracy and reliability in data collection:

1. **Calibrated Digital Lux Meter:** Measures ambient light intensity (Lux).
 - **Equipment Specification:** Measurements were conducted using a (HETLU031) Digital Lux Meter. This device features a silicon photocell sensor with a measuring range of 0–200,000 lux and a standard accuracy of \pm (4%+8).
 - **Calibration and Zeroing Procedure:** Zero-Adjustment (Dark Calibration): The sensor cap was securely placed over the photocell to block all light. The "Zero" function was activated to ensure the display read exactly 0.00 lux, confirming that internal electronic noise was not being recorded as light.
2. **Mobile GPS & Mapping Software (Google Maps / Google Earth):** Records geolocation coordinates (latitude and longitude) of accident-prone areas and landmarks.
3. **Environmental Factor Measurement Instruments and Methodologies:**
 - **Cloud Cover:** (SYNOP) Okta Scale. Ground-based manual observation where trained observers estimate fractional cover using the Okta Scale (0–8).
 - **Rainfall:** The Non-recording Rain Gauge. It is a simple graduated cylinder placed to collect a cumulative physical sample of rain water.
 - **Temperature:** Built-in Digital Sensors (in Lux Meters). Modern digital lux meters utilize integrated thermal sensors to convert thermal variations into electrical signals, allowing for simultaneous recording of illuminance and ambient temperature ($^{\circ}$ C).
 - **Soiling or Dust Accumulation:** To quantify Luminaire Dirt Depreciation (LDD) without physical debris collection, this study applied the Adjusted Panel Efficiency formula. By incorporating an efficiency loss fraction as a combined (PV) derating factor, environmental impacts were modeled systematically.

- VassarStats: is a web-based platform for statistical computation developed by Richard Lowry. It features JavaScript-based, point-and-click tools that allow users to perform a comprehensive range of analyses without the need for complex programming. Widely utilized in both educational and research settings, the site supports various statistical procedures, including t-tests, ANOVA, correlation, regression, and the calculation of probability distributions.

Data Collection and Analysis

Data collection was executed in three phases between 7:00 PM and 4:00 AM, following administrative coordination and official permission from local authorities, the PNP, and the BFP. In the preparation phase, digital lux meters were calibrated to a 0.00 lux baseline and GPS tools were readied for geolocation. During the field assessment, a 300-meter segment was divided into ten 30-meter intervals marked with chalk, where measurements were taken with strict adherence to safety protocols, including the use of reflective vests and helmets. To ensure data integrity, measurements were paused for passing vehicles to eliminate headlight interference, and sensors were protected during environmental stressors. Finally, data consolidation involved extracting solar irradiance values from the NASA POWER database and categorizing traffic accident records by time and cause to isolate the impact of visibility on road safety.

Data Treatment

The gathered data was analyzed using the following steps:

Step 1. Analysis of Traffic Safety and Accident Data

Frequency and Percentage Distribution: Following the framework established by Ackaah et al. (2020), the study was categorizing accident data from the Philippine National Police (PNP) and Bureau of Fire Protection (BFP) to identify specific characteristics and risk factors associated with nighttime conditions. A frequency and percentage distribution analysis was conducted to compare accidents occurring during the designated "True Night" window (7:00 PM – 4:00 AM) against daytime records to isolate visibility as a primary risk factor.

$$P = \frac{f}{n} \times 100$$

Where:

P = Percentage of nighttime accidents

f = Number of nighttime accidents (7:00 PM – 4:00 AM)

n = Total number of Vehicle Passes

Step 2. Illuminance Assessment Using Area Index

- Area Index (AI): The Area Index is used to determine the minimum number of measurement points for each road segment:

$$AI = \frac{L \times W}{H(L + W)}$$

Where:

L = length of the road segment (meters)

W = road width (meters)

H = pole height (meters)

Recommended Measurement Points Based on AI:

Area Index (AI)	Minimum Measurement Points
$AI < 1$	5
$1 \leq AI < 2$	10
$2 \leq AI < 3$	15
$AI \geq 3$	20

- Illuminance Measurement: Lux readings were taken at intervals determined by the AI for each segment to ensure representative sampling of darkness levels.
- Average Illuminance (E_{avg}): Calculated as the mean of measured Lux values:

$$E_{avg} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^N Lu x_i}{N}$$

Where:

Lux_i = individual readings,

N = total sampling points.

Values are compared against DPWH and IES road lighting standards.

(Note: Spearman Rank Correlation (R_s) Level of Significance = .05)

(Note. Adapted from "A New Approach to Street Lighting Design," by A. Sędziwy, 2015, LEUKOS, 12(3), p. 155

Geometric Parameters of the Study Area:

Parameter	Symbol	Value
Length of Segment	L	300m
Road Width (4-Lanes)	W	18m
Mounting Height (Pole)	H	11m
Calculated Area Index	AI	1.54
Grid Measurement Points	N	10 points

Figure No. 1. Technology Acceptance Model

The determined Area Index of 1.54 signifies a medium-to-wide road geometry relative to the pole height. This indicates that the road width (18 meters) is significant enough to require effective light distribution to prevent dark spots and ensure adequate visibility across all lanes. In support of this, Constantinos A. Bouroussis and Annika K. Jägerbrand (2022) emphasized that road lighting performance is strongly influenced by geometric factors such as road width, pole height, and spacing, where wider roads demand more uniform light distribution. Similarly, Mehmet Kayakuş and İsmail Serkan Üncü (2020) highlighted that uniformity is essential in achieving consistent illumination and safe driving conditions, while S. Fotios and R. Gibbons (2018) noted that roadway lighting standards rely on proper geometric considerations and sufficient measurement points to accurately assess lighting performance. In line with these principles, the use of 10 measurement points across the 300-meter segment ensures a statistically reliable sampling size to evaluate the uniformity of illuminance levels. From an Industrial Engineering perspective, an Area Index above 1.0 reinforces the need for high-quality lighting design and appropriate distribution patterns to minimize dark areas, particularly along the center lanes, thereby improving overall road safety and visibility.

Point measurements

A luxmeter measures illuminance at a specific point only. To determine the average illuminance in a space, it is necessary to take measurements at multiple points.

Grid system

To ensure accurate measurements, the space should be divided into a grid of equal squares, and the illuminance at the center of each square should be recorded

Solar lighting assessment environment layout

Step 3. Environmental Factor Consideration

Present environmental conditions that affect solar panel performance was measured and quantified:

- Rainfall and Cloud Cover: Real-time observations of rainfall and cloudiness was recorded to adjust the expected solar irradiance using an environmental derating factor:

$$E_{effective} = E_{ideal} \times F_{env}$$

Where:

$E_{effective}$ = effective energy generated under current conditions

E_{ideal} = theoretical energy based on peak sun hours

F_{env} = fraction representing reduction due to rain/clouds ($0 < F_{env} \leq 1$)

- Shading from Trees and Structures: On-site surveys were measure shadows cast on the panels at different times of the day. The energy loss due to shading was calculated as:

$$E_{shaded} = E_{ideal} \times (1 - S)$$

Where S = fraction of panel area shaded (e.g., 0.2 for 20% shaded).

- Other Environmental Conditions: Soiling or dust accumulation that reduce panel efficiency were noted, and an adjusted panel efficiency can be calculated:

$$\eta_{panel_adj} = \eta_{nominal} \times (1 - L_{env})$$

Where L_{env} = efficiency loss fraction due to environmental factors.

(Note: Operational Status: Failure is defined as a recorded illuminance of 0.00 lux during scheduled operational hours, indicating that the system's stored energy was insufficient to trigger the lamp's ignition threshold.)

(Note. Adapted from "Effects of weather conditions, light conditions, and road lighting on vehicle speed," by A. K. Jägerbrand and J. Sjöbergh, 2016, SpringerPlus, 5(1), p. 4.)

Step 4. Technical Design and Sizing Calculations

To evaluate the proposed solar-powered street lighting system, the following formulas were used:

- Total Daily Energy Load (E_d):

$$E_d = P_{LED} \times T_{op}$$

Where:

P_{LED} = wattage of the LED lamp,

T_{op} = operational hours (12 hours: 6:00 PM – 6:00 AM).

- Battery Capacity (C_{bat}): Ensures continuous operation during low sunlight:

$$C_{bat} = \frac{E_d \times D_{autonomy}}{V_{sys} \times DoD \times \eta_{bat}}$$

Where:

$D_{autonomy}$ = days of autonomy (target: 3 days),

V_{sys} = system voltage,

DoD = depth of discharge,

η_{bat} = battery efficiency.

- Solar Panel Sizing (P_{pv}): Determines the required panel size to meet energy demand:

$$P_{pv} = \frac{E_d \times F_{safety}}{H_{sun} \times \eta_{sys}}$$

Where:

F_{safety} = safety factor (1.3),

H_{sun} = peak sun hours (approx. 4.5–5.0 hours for Sibulan),

η_{sys} = system efficiency.

(Note. Adapted from "On the impact of safety requirements, energy prices and investment costs in street lighting refurbishment design," by M. Beccali et al., 2018, Energy, 165, pp. 739–759.)

Ethical Considerations

The researcher adhered to strict ethical standards and institutional policies throughout this solar street lighting assessment. Prior to the study, ethical approval was secured from Foundation University, and formal authorization for field measurements was obtained from the City Government of Dumaguete, specifically the City Engineering Office. Data collection focused strictly on technical metrics—such as roadway illuminance (Lux), solar component assessments, and traffic accident records—without the collection of personal or sensitive individual information. During nighttime fieldwork, safety protocols were implemented to ensure zero interference with traffic operations or public services. Post-collection, all data remained confidential, securely stored, and restricted to authorized personnel. Results are presented in an aggregated format to maintain institutional anonymity, with data archived and disposed of according to research guidelines. Furthermore, while AI tools were utilized to enhance manuscript clarity and grammar, all technical computations, Area Index calculations, and data analyses were independently conducted by the researcher to ensure academic integrity.

AI Usage and Assistance

This research was developed with the assistance of artificial intelligence tools specifically ChatGPT, Perplexity AI, Consensus, and Bohrium, which supported literature exploration, manuscript refinement, and the synthesis of evidence-based summaries. The integration of AI served to enhance clarity and organizational flow without compromising authorship integrity. All technical computations, data analyses, and final interpretations were independently conducted,

substantively edited, and validated by the researcher to ensure academic originality and strict adherence to ethical standards.

Results and Discussion

This chapter presents, analyzes, and interprets the data gathered in the study. It is organized into four parts: (1) the current lighting conditions of the existing street lighting along the Sibulan–Dumaguete Diversion Road, specifically in the Bajumpandan area; (2) the identification of areas with insufficient lighting and poor illuminance in terms of environmental and technical factors; (3) the vehicle accident rate in identified high-risk areas along the road; and (4) the relationship between vehicle accident rates and the current lighting conditions and illuminance levels. Data were collected through field measurements and secondary records and are presented in tables using appropriate statistical tools such as frequency counts, percentages, and correlation analysis. Each table is followed by a brief interpretation to explain and support the findings of the study.

Time	West P1	West P2	West P3	West P4	West P5	East P1	East P2	East P3	East P4	East P5
7:00 PM	10.2	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.7	2.5
8:00 PM	10.2	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.7	2.5
9:00 PM	10.2	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.7	2.5
10:00 PM	10.2	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.7	2.5
11:00 PM	10.2	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.7	2.5
12:00 AM	10.2	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.7	2.5
1:00 AM	10.2	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.7	2.5
2:00 AM	10.2	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.7	2.5
3:00 AM	10.2	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.7	2.5
4:00 AM	10.2	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.7	2.5

Table 1: Current Lighting Conditions on the Existing Street Lighting Along the Left Side of Sibulan Diversion Road Day 1-3

Figure 1. Graphical Presentation of Current Lighting Conditions on the Existing Street Lighting Along the Left Side of Sibulan Diversion Road Day 1-3

Monitoring the Diversion Road solar lighting system revealed critical failures, as shown in figure 1, with most segments on both the West and East sides exhibiting a total lack of functional illumination. Across all time intervals (7:00 PM to 4:00 AM) and over Day 1 to Day 3, the illuminance readings remain constant. On the West side, while Point 1 (P1) recorded a

low average of 10.20 lux, Points 2 through 5 consistently registered 0.00 lux throughout the observation period. Recorded light levels were elevated only in areas with supplemental electric lighting; otherwise, readings remained at 0.00 lux across the solar-powered segments. The system lacks sufficient illuminance, falling drastically short of the 50-lux OSHA safety benchmark and DPWH (2023) requirements. According to S. Fotios and R. Gibbons (2018), roadway lighting must meet minimum illuminance levels and maintain uniformity to ensure adequate visibility and safety, which is not observed in the present results. Analysis of the data indicates a highly uneven and inadequate lighting distribution from 7:00 PM to 4:00 AM. As shown in the provided graph, the data displays minimal distinct lines because the majority of measurement points yielded identical values of zero, causing them to overlap on the horizontal axis. While results are presented using two decimal places, the 0.00 lux readings at points West P2–P5 and East P1–P3 indicate that actual illumination is negligible, likely existing only at minute levels—such as 0.000012—that round down to zero. The measurable level at West P1 (10.20 lux) is attributed to a nearby electric streetlight rather than the solar system itself. On the East side, only P4 (0.70 lux) and P5 (2.50 lux) recorded measurable values, which remain significantly below recommended roadway standards. According to Constantinos A. Bouroussis and Annika K. Jägerbrand (2022), improper lighting design and poor distribution result in uneven illumination and the presence of dark zones along roadways.

Time	West	West	West	West	West	East	East	East	East	East
	P1	P2	P3	P4	P5	P1	P2	P3	P4	P5
7:00 PM	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	15.4	20.3
8:00 PM	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	15.4	20.3
9:00 PM	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	15.4	20.3
10:00 PM	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	15.4	20.3
11:00 PM	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	15.4	20.3
12:00 AM	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	15.4	20.3
1:00 AM	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	15.4	20.3
2:00 AM	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	15.4	20.3
3:00 AM	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	15.4	20.3
4:00 AM	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	15.4	20.3

Table 1.1: Current Lighting Conditions on the Existing Street Lighting Along the Right Side of Sibulan Diversion Road Day 1-3

Figure 2. Graphical Presentation of Current Lighting Conditions on the Existing Street Lighting Along the Right Side of Sibulan Diversion Road Day 1-3

Figure 2 shows that the data from the right side of the road across three days shows a highly uneven and consistently inadequate lighting distribution from 7:00 PM to 4:00 AM. The West side recorded 0.00 lux across all points (P1–P5), indicating a complete absence of functional illumination. On the East side, only P4 and P5 showed measurable levels—15.40 lux and 20.30 lux, respectively—attributed to nearby electric streetlights rather than the solar system. In contrast, points P1–P3 remained at 0.00 lux. As shown in the graph, minimal distinct lines appear because most measurement points yielded identical zero values and overlapped on the horizontal axis. While readings are presented to two decimal places, these 0.00 lux values indicate negligible illumination, likely existing only at minute levels (e.g., 0.000012) that round down. These persistent, near-zero readings suggest significant hardware malfunctions or insufficient battery storage. Ultimately, the system fails to meet the uniformity and safety requirements set by the DPWH (2023) and international standards lux OSHA safety benchmark. Across all time intervals (7:00 PM to 4:00 AM) and over Day 1 to Day 3, the illuminance readings remain constant. This consistency suggests a persistent issue in the solar lighting system, such as improper energy storage, insufficient solar charging, or system malfunction, causing the lights to fail in providing illumination throughout the night.

According to S. A. Adebayo (2017). and Bamisile (2025) consistent low illuminance over time indicates system inefficiency or failure, particularly in solar-powered lighting systems.

Environmental Category	Parameter/Observation	Recorded Value / Biological Factors
Cloud Cover	Average Cloud Cover (Day 1)	6/8 – 7/8 (Very Cloudy)
	Precipitation (Day 1)	8.5 mm Rainfall
Rainfall	Environmental Derating (F_{env})	0.54
	Effective Energy ($E_{effective}$)	786.6 Wh
Ambient Temperature	Ambient Temperature	24.8°C – 29.4°C
Physical Obstructions	East Side (P2 & P4)	Overhanging Branches
	West Side (P4 & P5)	Dense Vegetation
Other Factors (Soiling/Dust)	Adjusted Efficiency (η_{env})	0.19 (19%)
Combined Outcome	Operational Status	Total System Failure (0.00 Lux Recorded)/ Failure to Meet Standard Illuminance

Table 2.1: What Factors Affect the Area in Terms of Environmental Factors

Table 2.1 illustrates how the environmental data reveals a multi-layered energy deficit, where each recorded condition triggered a specific calculated impact on system performance, resulting in the observed 0.00 lux readings. On Day 1, the heavy 6/8 – 7/8 cloud cover caused significant Energy Attenuation, blocking the direct solar radiation necessary to reach peak charging voltage, while the 8.5 mm of rainfall resulted in a Charging Interruption that prematurely ended the energy harvest at dusk. According to Romero, R. (2023), heavy cloud cover is described as blocking the direct component of solar irradiance, leading to a “minimum value of daily energy” and incomplete charging even with several hours of exposure. These meteorological stressors are quantified by the Environmental Derating Factor (F_{env}) of 0.54, which created a massive Energy Deficit by stripping away 46% of the sun’s potential, and an Adjusted Panel Efficiency (η_{env}) of 19%, which established a Performance Gap below manufacturer specifications. Furthermore, physical obstructions like overhanging branches and dense vegetation caused a Voltage Drop and Localized Failure, physically reducing the energy harvest by up to 50% at specific points. Partial shading from trees and nearby structures is identified as a major cause of mismatch losses, hotspots, and module damage. A single shaded cell in a module can reduce power up to 50%, while multiple shaded cells can reduce output by up to 90% (Kushwaha, Nikhil, et al. 2023). The synthesis of these factors explains the Resultant Darkness; because the cumulative impact prevented the batteries from ever reaching the minimum threshold required to power the lamps, the system remained in a state of Total Failure across all time intervals, regardless of whether the subsequent days were rainy or sunny. (refer to Appendix C for environmental factor calculations page 83).

Technical Parameter	Existing Specifications	Calculated Requirement
Daily Energy Load	120W LED (Unregulated)	1,440 Wh/day
Battery Storage	768Wh (60Ah @ 12.8V)	3,952.9 Wh (310Ah)
Solar Panel Capacity	150W Monocrystalline	617.41 Wp
System Autonomy	3 Day (Observed)	3.5 Days
Operational Status	Total Failure	50 Lux (Compliance)

Table 2.2: What Factors Affect the Area in Terms of Technical Factors

Table 2.2 shows that the assessment reveals a critical lighting failure across all road segments, categorized as "Insufficient" due to a 95.18% deficiency relative to the 50-lux safety benchmark. This is primarily driven by an obsolete controller exceeding its 5-year limit and degraded battery capacity resulting from deep-discharge cycles (Smith, 2008) (refer to Appendix D page 87). Furthermore, existing 120W panels are undersized, failing to overcome the 0.54 environmental derating factor (F_{env}) caused by regional cloud cover and rainfall (Hassan et al., 2022; Matsumoto et al., 2020). To bridge the gap between the recorded 2.41 mean lux and the 50.00 lux ANSI/IESNA standard, a technical sizing model was developed using 120W luminaires on a 24V DC system to ensure reliability across an 18-meter road span. To prevent the premature failures common in tropical climates, the design utilizes a 0.80 Depth of Discharge and 0.85 efficiency (Rong, 2025). To ensure operational stability during Negros Oriental's monsoon season, a 3.5-day autonomy buffer is applied (Matsumoto et al., 2020). The study justifies a transition to a 617.41 Wp solar array with a 1.64 safety factor (Gonçalves et al., 2024). Based on a peak sun hour value of 4.5 hours, this redesign ensures full recharge capability despite persistent weather variability and "soiling" (Ayaz et al., 2024; Mohajeri et al., 2019). (refer to Appendix D for the technical factors and panel sizing calculations page 87)

Average Number of Accidents (2023-2025)	Average Total Vehicles (3-Night Observation)	Accident Rate (%)
2.33	6,102	0.038%

Table 3: Analysis of vehicle accident rates in identified high-risk areas

Table 3 presents the computed accident rate based on the average number of recorded accidents from 2023 to 2025 and the total vehicle count obtained from the three-night traffic observation. The results show that the accident rate is 0.038%, derived from an average of 2.33 accidents and a total of 678 observed vehicles during nighttime data collection. This indicates that accident occurrence is relatively low in relation to the total traffic volume within the study area (refer to Appendix E page 89). The computed mean value of accidents suggests that road incidents are not frequent across the three-year period covered by PNP records, while nighttime crash occurrences are generally influenced by multiple contextual and behavioral factors rather than traffic volume alone (Ackaah et al., 2020). The traffic volume obtained from the three-night observation reflects a moderate level of nighttime vehicle movement, primarily dominated by motorcycles. This implies that although there is continuous traffic flow in the area during nighttime, only a small proportion of vehicles are involved in road accidents (Li et al., 2023). The findings further suggest that traffic volume is not the primary contributing factor to accident occurrence in the study location. Instead, environmental conditions and human factors such as inadequate street lighting, reduced visibility, and delayed driver perception may have greater influence on nighttime crash risk (Fotios & Gibbons, 2018). Road lighting conditions significantly affect a driver's ability to detect hazards, react appropriately, and maintain safe driving behavior, especially in low-illumination environments (Jackett & Frith, 2012). These conditions are commonly associated with nighttime travel environments where reduced illumination can limit hazard detection and reaction time (Zhao et al., 2015). Despite the relatively low accident rate, the presence of recorded incidents over the years indicates the need for continuous improvement in road safety measures. Enhancing street lighting conditions, improving road signage visibility, and strengthening traffic monitoring in the area may help further reduce accident risks and ensure safer nighttime travel for road users (Agramelal et al., 2023).

Variables	r_s	p-value	Decision on H_0	Remark
Illuminance Level vs. Vehicle Accidents	0.017	0.945	Fail to Reject H_0	Not Significant

Table 4: The relationship between lighting conditions, and vehicle accident rates

Table 4 shows the computed p-value ($p = 0.945$) is greater than the 0.05 level of significance. Therefore, the decision is to fail to reject the null hypothesis (H_0). This means that there is no sufficient statistical evidence to conclude that illuminance level has a significant relationship with vehicle accidents in the study area (refer to Appendix F page 90). Recent studies support the idea that roadway lighting alone does not always show a strong direct relationship with accident occurrence, as road safety outcomes are influenced by multiple interacting factors such as traffic conditions, driver behavior, and roadway characteristics. Lighting effects are often indirect and context-dependent, which may explain the non-significant result of this study (Hou et al., 2022; Chen et al., 2024). Moreover, improvements in roadway lighting can enhance safety performance, but effectiveness depends on proper design, location, and supporting road features. Variations in lighting conditions across roadway segments may also influence crash trends, indicating that illuminance level alone is not a sufficient predictor of accident occurrence (Ziółkowski et al., 2024; Yang et al., 2019). Further supporting this, recent modeling studies indicate that not only illuminance level but also lighting uniformity and design quality significantly influence accident risk. Studies show that higher average lighting can reduce crash likelihood, but poor uniformity may increase accidents, reinforcing the need for proper system design rather than relying on brightness alone (Li et al., 2023).

The findings indicate that while lighting conditions are an important component of road safety, other factors such as driver behavior, traffic volume, road geometry, and environmental conditions may have a more dominant influence on vehicle accidents in the study area. Therefore, a comprehensive approach integrating engineering design improvements, enforcement, and road user behavior is necessary to effectively reduce road accidents.

Synthesis

The evaluation of solar-powered street lighting along the Dumaguete Diversion Road reveals a critical disparity between existing infrastructure and mandated safety requirements. While solar lighting is intended to provide a sustainable solution for highway safety, field assessments confirm that the current system is plagued by 0-lux failures, rendering many segments of the highway hazardous during nighttime hours. These failures are primarily attributed to technical deficiencies—specifically malfunctioning charge controllers and advanced battery degradation—compounded by environmental stressors such as lateral shading from local vegetation and significant soiling and dust accumulation.

The technical analysis demonstrates that the current illumination levels fall drastically short of the 50-lux OSHA safety benchmark, directly correlating with documented high-risk accident clusters in the area. To address these systemic gaps, this study transitioned from a purely observational assessment to a resilient technical redesign. By applying the Adjusted Panel Efficiency formula (η_{panel_adj}), the redesign accounts for a 5% environmental loss fraction (L_{env}), ensuring the system remains functional despite local pollution and weather variations.

The proposed solution—featuring 120-watt high-efficacy LED luminaires and a 617.41 Wp solar array—is engineered to provide a 3.5-day autonomy buffer. This ensures that even during periods of low solar irradiance typical of the regional climate, the lighting system maintains consistent performance. Ultimately, the synthesis of these findings suggests that achieving road safety in Dumaguete requires more than just hardware installation; it necessitates a data-driven approach to the current system.

Conclusion and Recommendations

The following inferences were derived based on the findings of the study:

1. The existing solar-powered street lighting system along the Bajumpandan segment is technically insufficient and unreliable, failing to meet required standards for nighttime visibility. Illuminance assessments revealed critical gaps, with most areas experiencing near-zero lighting levels and a uniformity ratio of 0.00, confirming a failure to eliminate dangerous dark spots and distribute light adequately.
2. Technical deficiencies—specifically inadequate battery capacity, poor charging efficiency, and component malfunctions—are the primary drivers of system failure rather than environmental factors. While cloud cover and shading affect performance, they do not negate the fact that the current system is significantly undersized for the 50-lux safety standard required for roadway conditions.
3. Poor lighting conditions are directly associated with higher accident occurrences, particularly in areas with zero illumination. The significant decrease in accidents following the localized restoration of functional streetlights highlights that reliable illumination is a vital practical intervention for reducing road collisions, regardless of weak statistical correlations caused by uniform data gaps.

In the light of the foregoing, these recommendations are suggested:

1. Local Government Units (LGUs) and the DPWH should prioritize a comprehensive technical upgrade, replacing existing units with a redesigned 120W LED luminaire system supported by 617.41 Wp solar panels and 310 Ah lithium batteries to ensure the 50-lux minimum standard and 0.40 uniformity ratio are met.
2. Relevant agencies should establish a rigorous maintenance and monitoring framework, including routine inspections and the installation of smart controllers for real-time fault detection, to prevent the recurrence of zero-lux conditions caused by degraded or defective components.
3. Environmental and site management must be standardized, involving regular vegetation trimming to prevent panel shading and scheduled cleaning of solar arrays to minimize efficiency losses caused by dust, dirt, and vehicular emissions.
4. Infrastructure policy and funding should be aligned to enforce strict standards for solar street lighting design and installation, prioritizing continuous operation in high-risk zones like intersections to improve driver visibility and reduce collision risks.

5. Future research should explore the integration of IoT-based monitoring and adaptive motion-sensor lighting controls to enhance energy efficiency, while conducting long-term lifecycle cost analyses to develop standardized, durable solutions for wider regional application.

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Competing Interests Statement

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this article.

Data Availability Statement

Data sharing is not applicable to this article as no new data were created or analyzed in this study; all data used were obtained from previously published sources as cited in the reference list.

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Appendices

No appendices are attached to this study.